

A new species of the genus *Pidonia* Mulsant, 1863 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from the Russian Far East

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Abstract: *Pidonia* (*Cryptopidonia*) *petrovi* sp. n. similar to Japanese *P. (C.) hylophila* Kuboki, 1977 is described from the Russian Far East.

Introduction

The genus *Pidonia* Mulsant, 1863 was represented in Russian fauna up to now by 10 Far Eastern species of 4 subgenera (Danilevsky, 2014): 7 species of *P. (Pseudopidonia* Pic, 1900), 1 - *P. (Mumon* Hayashi, 1968), 1 - *P. (Omphalodera* Solsky, 1873) and 1 - *P. (Cryptopidonia* Kuboki, 1981). A single species of *Cryptopidonia* - *P. (C.) kurosawai* (Ohbayashi et Hayashi, 1960) is known in Russia from south Kuriles only. It is very numerous on Kunashir and was recorded from Iturup. The species is widely distributed on Hokkaido and northern Honshu. Now a species of *P. (Cryptopidonia)* was unexpectedly discovered in the south of Primorye Region. It is described below as a new species.

The subgenus *P. (Cryptopidonia)* is characterized by short and wide body, smoothly rounded pronotum without longitudinal carina, eyes without emargination, 3rd antennal joint much longer than two first combined.

Material and method

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. Both photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

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Taxonomy

Pidonia (Cryptopidonia) petrovi sp. n.

Figs 1-10

Type locality. Russia, Primorsky Region, Shkotovo district, pass Serebryanyi, 43°20'34.76"N, 132°57'7.38"E.

Description. Body totally black; head elongated; genae long about two times only shorter than eye diameter; temples indistinct; eyes big, with very small notch; last palpal joint triangular, oblong; last labial joint also triangular, but short, about as long, as wide; antennae filiform, not thickened distally; from black to brown; often dark basally and lightened distally; male antennae nearly reaching elytral apex, female antennae reaching last elytral third; the longest 3rd antennal joint much longer than two first combined; 5th joint longer than 4th; prothorax globular, without longitudinal central elevation; in male slightly longer than basal width, in females - slightly longer or slightly shorter, with wide lateral tubercles; with deep anterior and posterior constrictions; very short fine pronotal recumbent pubescence hardly distinct; short and narrow central pronotal line almost absent in the holotype, or totally absent in certain females, or rather distinct and strongly shining in others; elytra parallelsided or with sides a little converging posteriorly in the holotype and certain females; from light brown to black with several small yellow spots, without erect setae, with very fine short indistinct pubescence; elytral punctation very fine and dense; male elytra about 2.3 times longer than basal width, in female - from 2.1 to 2.2 times; elytral design strongly variable; elytra can be totally light brown (as in holotype) or black with several yellow spots; the most development case shows each black elytron with central yellow half ring, two small yellow spots anteriorly and a short wide yellow bar posteriorly; all stages of reduction can be observed to lighter conditions; the darkest versions consist of small yellow spot from 5 to 3 on each elytron; legs with black femora and partly lightened tibiae and tarsi; body length in holotype (male) - 9.1 mm, humeral width - 2.7 mm; in paratypes (females) - 8.8- 9.3 mm, width - 2.4-2.9 mm.

Figs 1-10. *Pidonia (Cryptopidonia) petrovi* sp. n.: 1 - male, holotype, Russia, Primorsky Region, Shkotovo district, pass Serebryani, 31.5.2023, A.V. Petrov leg.; 2, 6-9 - females, Primorsky Region, Shkotovo district, pass Serebryani, 43°20'34.76"N, 132°57'7.38"E, 31.5.2023; 3-5, 10 - females, Primorsky Region, Shkotovo district, Anisimovka environs, Mt. Falaza, 25-27.5.2023.

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Differential diagnosis. New species differs from most *Pidonia* by relatively long genae, which are usually very narrow in *Pidonia*; because of that character and big lateral thoracic tubercles it is not close to any other *Pidonia* species; it looks similar to *P. (C.) hylophila* Kuboki, 1977, but that species has short head, very long antennae (in females longer than body), wide prothorax with small lateral tubercles and very narrow genae.

Material. Holotype, male, Russia, Primorsky Region, Shkotovo district, pass Serebryanyi, 43°20'34.76"N, 132°57'7.38"E, 31.5.2023, A.V. Petrov leg. - author's collection; paratypes, 10 females - author's collection and collection of A.V. Shamaev (Moscow): 5 females with same label and 5 females from same district, Anisimovka environs, Mt. Falaza, 25-27.5.2023, A.V. Petrov leg.

Etymology. The new species is dedicated to Aleksandr Valentinovich Petrov, who collected the type series.

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